

A prospective study on evaluating the clinical and functional outcome of limb salvage surgery and amputation in distal femoral osteosarcoma patients

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Abstract: Aim: The main aim of this study was to assess the survival, recurrence, complications and also the quality of life (QOL) in distal femoral osteosarcoma (OSA) patients managed by limb salvage surgery (LSS), either by a prosthesis, resection or graft and by amputation or disarticulation. **Methods and Materials:** 44 distal femoral osteosarcoma patients were enrolled, where 20 patients were managed by custom- designed endoprosthetic arthroplasty (LSS1), 16 patients only by resection and bone graft (LSS2), while only 8 patients were managed by amputation. A comparison was made between the patients undergoing LSSs and amputation/disarticulation based on postoperative survival rates, postoperative recurrence, and complications. The impact of the patient's QOL was also evaluated based on standard SF-36 form and MSTS scoring system. **Results:** The results of our study showed that the incidence of femoral OSA was higher in <20 years (65.91%), where M: F was 1.44:1 (p=0.512). We had 44 distal femoral OSA patients included in this study. The mean survival of patients with LSS1 was 0.85 years, 1.48 years for LSS2 patients (1.165 years in LSS, which is LSS1 + LSS2) and 1.6 years for amputees respectively by means of Kaplan Meier survival analysis (P = 0.0218). The total complication free patients was 36.36 % (LSS1+ LSS2 43.18%, amputation group 2.27% %, p = 0.0096). The mean MSTS score was 62% (range, 46%-83%) with significantly lower results in amputations (p = 0.0001). The QOL assessment done by SF-36 revealed a better state of LSS patients. The sarcoma led to emotional and functional disturbances in patients who underwent amputation (p < 0.05). **Conclusion:** LSS for distal femoral osteosarcoma is superior to amputation due to its better emotional and functional outcome.

Keywords: Osteosarcoma, limb salvage surgery, amputation, prosthesis, resection, sarcoma

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Introduction

This century is a highly innovative era in surgery due to surgical techniques advancements, but for patients diagnosed with femoral osteosarcoma (OSA), amputation is still considered a dominant surgical treatment^{1,2}. With the rise in adjuvant therapies and neoadjuvant chemotherapies, limb sparing surgery is becoming a more acceptable option for distal femoral OSA. It is a scarcely occurring malignant bone tumor (20% of primary bone cancers) and is the second most common primary malignant tumor of bone^{3,4}. It has a higher incidence in the distal femur, proximal tibia (around the knee joint), followed by proximal humerus, and distal tibia. OSA's incidence in the distal tibia is 19%, while 80% is in the proximal tibia.⁵ The tumor can be seen at any bony site; however, most commonly found to occur in long bones of the extremities near the metaphyseal growth plates, especially within the medullary cavity. It appears that the incidence in the younger age group of individuals (10-25 years) is higher than in other groups^{4,6}. The exact cause of the tumor pathology is still unknown, although some have associated it with some risk factors. It is investigated and diagnosed thoroughly by clinical, radiological, and pathophysiological examinations with some characteristic features like a Codman's triangle, Sunburst appearance with Sharpey's fibers. A treatment modality includes neoadjuvant chemotherapy for osteosarcoma patients, no matter what the surgical approaches are. A pre-operative therapy has proven to shrink the tumor facilitating surgical excision of the tumor and effectively treat micro-metastasis as early as possible with a significant therapy response (>90% tumor necrosis), leading to a better prognosis. Surgical approaches for managing the osteosarcoma patients are limb salvage reconstructions surgeries or amputations.

Different types of limb sparing techniques are available for femoral OSA, such as megaprosthesis, allograft, and autograft bone reconstruction techniques.^{1,7,8} Patients undergoing replacement with megaprosthesis have survival rates of 40-100%, a function of 50-93%, and complications of 17-60%, while for the patients undergoing bone reconstruction, survival is 40-100%, the function is 53-100%, and complications are 12-92%. However, for amputation, survival is 84-100%, and the complication rate ranges from 12-70%.^{9,10} Due to advancements in limb sparing techniques, surgeries have been possible without influencing the femoral OSA patients' survival rate.^{11,12} MSTs scores range from 100-50% for limb sparing surgery and 90-53% for amputation patients of OSA.¹³ Although various studies have different findings for survival and function, the survival rates after limb-sparing surgeries range from 0.5-24 years, while for amputation, it ranges from 3-5 years.

Regarding various studies on OSA, controversies are still prevalent to decide which the better treatment option is^{7,8,14}. Therefore, our study's main aim was to analyze the survival rate, recurrence, and complication in patients who underwent limb-sparing surgeries (endoprosthesis, resection, and graft) and amputations. Moreover, to check the health status, quality of life, and functional scores of the operated patients with distal femoral osteosarcoma we assessed the operative measure's outcome and analyzed the patient's mental, social and psychological status. Our objective was to determine which treatment option would be better by means of comparison between limb salvage reconstruction surgery techniques and amputation for the distal femoral osteosarcoma patients. We also aim to obtain distinction findings that might be vital for the researchers, oncologists, and orthopedic surgeons to understand themselves and counsel the individuals who have been considered for the limb salvage and reconstruction surgeries or amputation after the diagnosis of the disease.

Fig. 1: A case of 12y old female patient with distal femoral OSA. She underwent disarticulation surgery at the right hip joint

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- To compare the efficacy of the limb salvage technique and amputation in femoral osteosarcoma
- To assess the disease-free survival in femoral osteosarcoma patients after the treatment approached
- To assess the quality of life by the SF-36 and MSTS scoring system in femoral osteosarcoma operated patients who have survived

METHODS AND MATERIALS USED

- Type of study - This is a prospective comparative hospital-based study.
- Place of study - This study was conducted in the Department of Orthopedic Surgery, 1stAffiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China.
- Duration of study - This study was conducted during the course from September 2018 to December 2021

Sample size:

- The prevalence of Osteosarcoma (\bar{p}) = 2.4%
- Tabulated value of Z at 95% CI = 1.96
- Allowable error (e) = 5% (0.05)

$$\frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{e^2}$$

- Sample size (n) =

$$= \frac{1.96^2 \times 2.4/100 \times (1-2.4/100)}{0.05^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.024 \times 0.976}{0.0025} = 36$$

Sampling Method:

The non-probability sampling method was used in this study. A total of 44 cases fulfilling the inclusion criteria during the study period were taken for the study.

Sampling selection:

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients with pathological diagnosis of distal femoral osteosarcoma
- No metastatic disease, a primary malignant disease
- Osteosarcoma lesions found with complete clinical data
- Adequate kidney and liver functions

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with cancer other than distal femoral osteosarcoma
- Non-measurable disease
- Disease influencing the treatment of tumor
- Deranged kidney and liver functions
- The femoral OSA patient who was still on chemotherapy

Research questions

- Comparison between the time of union, survival time of reconstruction
- Overall survival of the patients improves or not
- Is limb salvage helpful or amputation
- Is the function of the limb is compromised or not
- Recurrence of the tumor cells after the operation no matter what the procedure
- Complications following the different surgical techniques
- The psychological outcome of the patient

STUDY DESIGN

Patients with a lump or mass that could be felt through the skin close to the lower end of femoral bone or the knee joints, and who had complaints of bone or joint pain in the lower extremity were included in the study.

Almost all the patients were evaluated in the out-patient department of orthopaedics. A detailed history and physical examination, mostly lower extremity examination, were conducted. After clinical examination, the suspected cases of the tumor were sent for imaging studies (X-ray, CT scan, MRI) to confirm the diagnosis and planned for biopsy.

Once the provisional diagnosis of the sarcoma was made, patients were advised for inpatient admission in the department of orthopaedics for final diagnosis. All the baseline investigations, including complete blood count, blood sugar levels, liver function test, renal function test, chest X-ray, and ECG, were sent. Pre-operative serum levels ALP, LDH values were taken. A biopsy was performed on every patient once the diagnosis was confirmed. After the positive biopsy (pathological) reports in each patient confirming osteosarcoma diagnosis, neoadjuvant chemotherapies were commenced. Ifosfamide and doxorubicin were given in every cycle.

Additionally, methotrexate and cisplatin were given, depending on the patient's physical condition and efficiency. Pre-operatively three cycles and postoperatively six cycles of chemotherapies were given. After the completion of the cycles of chemotherapy, they were advised for hospital admissions. All patients were counseled for various means of surgical procedures available for their illness. As per the requirement of the patient's disease condition and consent, the operative methods were processed.

After all the preparations, custom made endoprosthesis, joint reconstructions, or amputation were decided. Once the operative procedure was decided, all patients underwent pre-anesthetic check-up by an anesthetist and prepared for operation—no matter the procedure, the tumor mass specimen after the resection was sent for further histopathological examination. After the open biopsy, pathological confirmation of osteosarcoma was planned for post-surgery chemotherapy cycles.

In the recent years, custom-made limb sparing surgery using endoprosthetic joint replacements or megaprosthesis has been becoming prevalent. They can replace the entire bone as well as both adjacent joints. Its merit allows immediate joint stability and weight-bearing to provide higher joint functions leading to a higher functional status. There are chances of prosthesis implant failure, loosening, and infection as postoperative complications in LSS. However, our study did not have any rejection cases. The parts of the implant in the joint would wear out with time, and eventually, it might be required to replace at some point.

In distal femoral OSA, limb sparing surgery was done by a total femoral endoprosthetic replacement, which has been the best choice.¹⁵(figure 2) While in patients who did not require arthroplasty, only resection with graft (allograft, autograft) implantation was done. The graft could be a fibula graft or a commercially available graft.

Fig. 2: A case of 8yo female patient, pre-operative and post-operative images of distal femoral osteosarcoma case who had a total femoral endoprosthesis implanted

Fig. 3: A case of 17Y M, X-ray: AP view of both lower limbs and left leg lateral view, before and after the tumor resection of distal femoral osteosarcoma and after the resection was done endoprosthesis was implanted. Figure 3 shows the MRI of this patient

For distal femoral limb sparing surgery, fibula graft followed by arthrodesis was done using plates (Titanium or stainless steel) and screws. Among the various methods available for the distal femoral reconstruction, we tried various methods. Some of the methods used as a reconstruction procedure were; using a pasteurized autograft, allograft,

autogenous fibular graft, and the megaprosthesis. Also, tumor's wide en-bloc resection and bone recycling using liquid nitrogen or just hypertonic saline or gentamicin at high temperature for half an hour or the portion was either ablated with microwave-induced hyperthermia generating heat ablating very high volumes of tumor sections. The femoral artery was checked for their salvage ability, and reconstructive surgery was done with adequate fixation.

For the distal regions, above-knee amputation or disarticulation surgery was performed with proper planning in patients who were not suitable candidates for LSS (figure 1). Tentative markings were done over the amputation planned area. While amputating, resection was done at least 2 cm or 3 cm proximal to the affected region determined by radiological examination and obtaining sufficient soft tissue coverage with adequate remaining portion of the limb. Stump was created with standard surgical procedures.

Patients were divided into three categories based on the surgical procedure decided:

Group A (LSS1): 22 patients who had endoprosthetic arthroplasty

Group B (LSS2): 14 patients who had resection with or without bone graft.

Group C (amputation): 8 patients who had amputation.

Fig. 4: MRI of left knee of the patient from figure 2

Quality assessment

There is an increasing demand for analyzing the quality of life and functional outcomes in patients with OSA. QOL is an independent survival and response predictor, which plays a significant role in evaluating the cancer patients. In some studies, results were significantly better in limb sparing surgery (by means of TESS and MSTS scoring system). On the other hand, other studies did not report to have a remarkable one, so the controversy is still prevalent in deciding which has better outcomes. In this study, we chose MSTS and SF-36 forms to assess the health conditions of operated patients. SF-36 and MSTS scoring system were done in three groups. Patients who had to undergo secondary amputation due to recurrence were included in the amputation group and likewise for secondary prosthetic knee arthroplasty in group LSS1.

Each patient was asked specific questions, a standard questionnaire designed to assess the quality of life. The SF-36 form consisted of 36 questions that set nine parameters, which were 1) physical functioning (PF), 2) role limitations due to physical health (PH), 3) role limitations due to emotional problems (EP), 4) energy or fatigue (EF), 5) emotional wellbeing (EW), 6) social functioning (SF), 7) Pain (P), 8) General Health (GH) and 9) Health change (HC). Moreover, range from 100 optimal to zero being the poorest.

The MSTS scoring system, which was given to every patient, comprised of 6 parameters: 1) pain, 2) function, 3) emotional acceptance, 4) use of external support, 5) walking ability 6) gait alterations. Each parameter was scored from 0-5 with a total score of 0-30; the higher the score was, the higher the function. The functional scoring system was

categorized into three score groups: 1) <49% Fair; 2) 50-75% good; and 3) >75% excellent. MSTS scores range from 50-100% for Limb sparing surgery and 53-90% for amputation patients of OSA.

Post-operative follow-up: The scheduled follow-up time is one month, three months, six months, nine months, and 12 months. A post-operative X-ray and chest CT scans were done on each follow-up. After one year, patients were suggested to come for follow up every six months. Any complications which cannot be detected by X-ray were confirmed by MRI and CT scans. If signs recur, then administer further treatment; for any patient who had a resectable tumor growth, we proceeded with re-resection. If the tumor is not able to be excised, they should be advised for limb amputation or disarticulation. If the location is not reachable, the patient should be suggested for radiotherapy.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The statistical program SPSS 25 for windows 8.1 and Microsoft Excel 2013 was used for the analysis. Tests such as the Chi-square test, student's t-test were used to calculate the p-values, while for the survival, the Kaplan-Meier analysis was done. Values were compared, differences between variables were analyzed. Moreover, a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered to be significant.

RESULTS

Our study consisted of 44 patients, among which 26 were males and 18 females with a mean age of 21.58 years (range, 8-60 years). The decision regarding the surgical procedure was based on biopsy and staging. Based on the surgical procedure decided, patients were divided into three groups, 1) LSS1 (with endoprosthesis), 2) LSS2 (resection with or without bone graft), and 3) amputation. Of 44 patients initially, 20 (45.45%) patients had custom-designed endoprosthetic arthroplasty, 16 (36.36%) patients underwent resection and bone graft, while only 8 (18.18%) patients underwent amputation. The male to female ratio for LSS1 was 1:1, LSS2 was 2.2:1, and amputation was 1.67:1, overall M: F ratio in our study was found to be 1.44:1 ($p = 0.512$). LSS1 patients in the age group < 20 years were 15, 20-40 years were five and >40 years were 0, in LSS2 patients in the age group < 20 years were 12, 20-40 years were 4 and >40 years were 0 while amputated patients in the age group < 20 years were 2, 20-40 years were 2 and >40 years were 4 ($p = 0.0004$). In total, 36 patients had limb sparing surgery in the initial phase, among which 4 had to undergo secondary endoprosthetic arthroplasty after wide en-bloc resection. In comparison, 4 patients had to undergo a secondary amputation, and 8 had primary amputation (Table 1, 2). The total number of patients with distal femoral OSA patients were 44 (20 LSS1, 16 LSS2 & 8 amputation) ($p = 0.0096$). The mean and median survival of patients with LSS1 was 0.85 years, 0.68 years, LSS2 was 1.48, 1.47 and amputation were 1.60 years, 1.41 years respectively with overall mean survival time of 1.22 years. The number of deaths was 6. Among all, 25 patients had various post-operative complications, which were pain and swelling (11), joint stiffness (3), joint effusion (1), wound and skin infection (5), numbness (6), and lung metastasis (6) (Table 2). Only pain complaints without swellings were seen higher in amputation patients.

Variables	LSS1	LSS2	Amputation	Total	
No. of Patients	20	16	8	44	
Gender					<i>P = 0.51177</i>
Male	10	11	5	26	
Female	10	5	3	18	
Age					
<20 years	15	12	2	29	
20-40 years	5	4	2	10	<i>P = 0.0004</i>
>40 years	0	0	4	5	

Table 1: Table showing age, gender, and location distribution of the distal femoral osteosarcoma in the three groups LSS1, LSS2, and amputations patients

Complications	LSS1	LSS2	Amputation	Total	
Pain + Swelling	8	3	0	11	
Joint Stiffness	1	2	0	3	
Joint Effusion	1	0	0	1	
Wound and Skin Infection	4	0	1	5	
Numbness	2	2	2	6	
Recurrence	1	6	4	11	<i>P=0.0096</i>
Lung Metastasis	0	3	3	6	
Secondary Operation	0	4	0	4	
Amputation	0	2	0	2	
Mega Prosthesis	0	2	0	2	

Table 2: Table showing Complications that were seen in LSS1, LSS2, and amputation patients

The recurrence was seen higher in the LSS2 group (6) while in amputation (4) and in LSS1 (1) ($p = 0.0096$). A higher complication rate was seen in amputated patients (83.5%) compared to patients who had endoprosthesis (30.7%) and with those who had resection (65.8%). Complete complication-free patients were 19 [14 (69.3%) LSS1, 5 (34.2%) LSS2, 5, 1 (16.5%) amputee] showing higher numbers in limb salvaged patients (Table 3). After the surgery, patients who are still alive and those who had LSS had continuity in their previous lifestyle.

Fig. 5: A comparison between complications in patients underwent LSS1, LSS2 and amputations

Operative method	LSS1+LSS2	Amputation	Total	
Complications	17	7	28	
Complication free	19	1	16	<i>P = 0.0096</i>
Total patients	36	8	44	

Table 3: Table showing a comparison between complications and complication-free in patients who underwent LSS and amputation

The mean survival time was 0.85 years for LSS1 patients, 1.48 years for LSS2 patients (1.165 years in LSS, which is LSS1 + LSS2) and 1.6 years for amputees respectively by means of Kaplan Meier survival analysis ($P = 0.0218$).

We evaluated the SF-36 form questionnaire of 44 patients (20 LSS1, 16 LSS2, and 8 amputations). 6 patients died due to recurrences and lung metastases in the process of follow up. The health survey done on all revealed that patients who had limb-sparing surgeries were in a better state than those who went through amputation. Moreover, all parameters of QOL were found to be significant for limb sparing surgery ($p \leq 0.05$). Comparing with the other cancer survivors, sarcoma survivors have relative physical limitations with lesser SF-36 scores (Figure 7). The sarcoma led to higher emotional disturbance in amputated patients than in limb sparing surgery patients ($p = 0.0475$).

SF-36	PF	PH	EP	EF	EW	SF	PAIN	GH	HC
LSS1	77.2	87.1	73	86.7	91.1	90	85.8	89.9	84.6
LSS2	70.8	72.3	59	68.5	82.3	80.4	78.3	80.3	74
Amputation	55	46	34.3	60	58	58.2	61.9	53	57
P-value	0.0196	0.0599	0.0294	0.0348	0.0736	0.0637	0.0365	0.0733	0.0364

Table 4: QOL SF-36 form Questionnaire mean values obtained from patients of distal femoral osteosarcoma operated cases

Fig. 6: QOL SF-36 form questionnaire mean values obtained in the form of a graph

The mean MSTS score was 62% (46%-83%). The amputees had a significantly lower score in comparison to limb sparing surgery. Patients had complaints of pain, either due to altered gait, due to operative measures, or either due to prosthetic issues. The patients who underwent amputation had difficulty maintaining normal gait, required more external support, and were emotionally weaker; pain problems were seen higher and emotionally and functionally dependent on others. Thus the mean functional results were excellent in LSS1 (83%), good in LSS2 (55%), while fair in amputees (46%) (Table 5)(Figure 6).

Mean MSTS	Pain	Function	Emotional	External Support	Functional Independence	Gait	TOTAL	MSTS
LSS 1	3.4	4.3	3.1	4.2	5	5	25	83%
LSS 2	3.9	3.1	1.8	1	2.8	3.8	16.5	55%
Amputation	2.2	2.5	3	3.2	1.5	1.5	13.9	46%
P-value	0.0340	0.0424	0.0149	0.0727	0.1020	0.1333	0.0375	0.0008

Table 5: Table showing different mean MSTS score results obtained from the three groups LSS1, LSS2, and amputations, in distal femoral osteosarcoma patients who were operated. They were graded as 1) <49% Fair; 2) 50-75% good; and 3) >75% excellent

Figure 7 MSTS score mean results obtained from patients under LSS1, LSS2, and amputation groups

The results of our study favoured limb salvage surgeries for distal femoral osteosarcoma regardless of its location, but complication rates were seen higher than in amputated patients. However, during our study, we only had a few patients with amputation. As for the disease's rarity, the sample size was less; the duration of this study was not sufficient to evaluate the five-year survival rates; our study only provides us with data analysis for a short time.

DISCUSSION

Among the treatment options for bone sarcomas, Multidisciplinary treatment (MDT) has been proved to be a better choice. LSS is the best way of management for distal femur. The effectiveness of limb sparing surgery in patients with distal femoral OSA is still controversial. However, some studies show that megaprosthesis implant has proved to be effective.¹⁶ Skill-wise reconstructive surgery for attaining sufficient fixation in the distal region is challenging due to its limited surrounding tissue and gross bone loss, leading to a higher complication rate with inadequate soft tissue coverage. It is a challenge to overcome the soft tissue coverage and joint mechanics in limb sparing surgery. LSS also has higher chances of muscle and nerve damage leading to higher complications than in amputated patients. Studies have proved to favour limb sparing surgery due to its higher functional and emotional outcomes in both proximal and distal osteosarcomas.

Allograft bone can be bought from commercial bone banks and benefit from restoring the wide en-bloc resected portion of bone and delaying joint replacement.^{17,18} The implant helps stability, strength, and modularity with the bone restoring and soft tissue benefits conferred by the bone graft. It allows better soft tissue repair and joint function, especially in the distal femur.^{17,19,20} But, usually does not re-vascularize and is subject to nonunion and infections 15% and fracture 27%, requiring additional surgeries. Complications are challenging and often require further surgery, including at times amputation.¹⁸ Due to the high rate of recurrences after resections and grafts (allograft, autograft), few cases eventually lead to amputation.²¹ Gaston et al. reported a high local recurrences rate of 40% in LSS, although long-term survival, and concluded that LSS should be attempted whenever possible. JRenard et al. and Mavrogenis et al. both also reported complications in LSS more than in amputation¹³. Schragar et al. reported overall mortality to be 35% more in amputation. Ayerza et al. also reported a better survival rate. Aksnes et al. concluded the bone sarcoma patients who survived managed well with an overall better quality of life, adjusting their physical limitations with more impaired function in amputees.

Some surgeons still choose amputations, while many choose limb-sparing surgeries due to their high emotional value. Post neoadjuvant chemotherapy, most surgeons, after an MRI, select and opt for amputation implying that the therapy does not alter much to the tumor instead decreases the oedema.

The metastatic disease typically develops haematogenously, with the most common metastasis site being the lungs, followed by other bones.²² Amputation leads to early blockage of further spreading or metastasis of sarcoma to other vital organs leading to death. At the present stage, traditional amputation is still considered a choice among surgeons for OSA, although it has a

5-year overall survival rate of only 10-20%. In contrast, advancements in adjuvant chemotherapies and radio imaging techniques limb-sparing surgery has been a viable emerging choice providing better results and preventing metastasis of the sarcoma. Amputation is thought to be less expensive than limb-sparing surgery procedures; however, some studies have proved to be the opposite.²³ According to a survey done by Sluga et al., his team concluded that there were not many differences in the overall survival of a patient who underwent amputation and limb-sparing surgeries.²⁴ Amputation is a suitable oncological procedure and can even maintain an athletic lifestyle as post-amputation patients can have the pleasure to use an external prosthesis, thereby maintaining a higher activity level.¹⁸

The quality assessment was done according to the standard SF-36, a form which is proven to be reliable and validated in the Chinese population.^{25,26} It has been accepted for quality evaluation and assessment. Our study showed that those who had endoprosthesis arthroplasty (LSS1 group) had better scores of SF-36, MSTS, and fewer complications. However, while considering only the LSS2 group, the recurrence rates and complications were found to be a bit higher. Recurrences and complications in the amputations were higher than in limb-sparing surgeries. Johansen et al. reported a significantly higher functional score. Our findings of having a better functional outcome in LSS than in amputation are also consistent with other studies. Cosmetic and social factors also significantly influence LSS over amputation, due to which limb sparing surgery is preferred over amputations.

Our study also concludes to have assessed a better QOL and higher MSTS score compared to other studies, proving a higher functional and emotional outcome in limb sparing surgery than in amputation. Our study confirmed that patients receiving amputation had lower MSTS scores than patients undergoing limb-salvage surgery. Moreover, based on the Chinese version MSTS and SF-36, we were able to obtain highly consistent and reliable results in favor of limb-salvage surgery and prove that distal femoral osteosarcoma patients can attain an excellent functional outcome in the long-term.

Our results showed that LSS resulted in a higher 5-year overall-survival (OS) rate than amputation and higher MSTS scores, higher QOL. These results confirm that limb salvage surgical choice is the better surgical alternative, with many advantages than the amputation.

STRENGTH AND LIMITATION

Our study has several strengths and limitations; this study only confines to one institute and the study period is short due to which sample size is small. The follow-up time of the patients was short. Therefore, more time is required. Our hospital has excellent multidisciplinary coordination with an excellent laboratory for investigations, highly advanced technologies for radiological examinations, including well-trained radiologists, skilled surgeons, and pathologists. Furthermore, clinical imaging, routine investigations, and pathological findings are exceptionally reliable and sensitive to detect cancer early. The neoadjuvant chemotherapies are highly reliable, sensitive, and useful for osteosarcoma patients. We are therefore guided to a better treatment plan with a good prognosis. This convenient and straightforward detection, leading to timely neoadjuvant chemotherapies for osteosarcoma, has given hope for early diagnosis and timely treatment for a lesser chance of recurrence, complications, and better survival, making it possible for sarcoma patients to have a better quality of life.

TAKE HOME MESSAGE TO THE READERS

Osteosarcoma is a rare pathological condition, nevertheless, it should not be left out in the differential diagnosis in patients with swelling, pain, and other symptoms. If any patient with or without familial history of osteosarcoma has

been presented with complaints of pain, a lump or mass that could be felt over the skin, an immediate diagnosis has to be attained with the help of radiological imaging. The diagnosis can be further confirmed by means of bone biopsy.

CONCLUSION

Relatively lower values of SF-36 scores with a relative limitation to limb salvage surgical procedures were seen in the distal femoral osteosarcoma patients who are still surviving after the amputation. The MSTS mean functional results were excellent in limb salvage surgery adjacent to the tibial region with megaprosthesis and were satisfactory in patients with other limb-sparing surgeries. The patients who underwent amputation had a significantly lower score, the causing to have worse MSTS functional assessment. Complication rate was seen higher in amputation patients, whereas patients with megaprosthesis had least complications. Only one patient who underwent the megaprosthesis implantation had a recurrence. The cases of recurrence in our study were highest in limb salvage reconstruction surgeries, but were high in amputation patients also. Our results showed that LSS resulted in a higher 5-year OSA rate in comparison to amputation, although survival was seen to be similar in all groups.

Since the survival is similar in all groups, it would be worth accepting the higher risks for whom limb sparing surgery is feasible by strict follow-up. On the other hand, amputations should only be reserved for those having local recurrences and in patients resistant to adjuvant chemotherapies.

In conclusion, LSS is the better treatment option for femoral osteosarcoma for distal end based on its better QOL, MSTS scores, survivability, recurrence rates, and complication-free survival. Thus, LSS is superior over amputation.

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